

ZENODO STUDENT VOICE COMMUNITY: STUDENT VOICE FRAMEWORK AND ASSOCIATED DOCUMENTS

The documentation saved in this Zenodo Student Voice community provides you with resources to run an effective step-by-step student voice process through an academic year.

The documentation saved in this community should be read in the order set out below.

The first document, 'Student Voice Framework – Introduction for Responsible Staff' contains hyperlinks to all of the other documents listed below.

0A Student Voice Framework - Introduction for Responsible Staff

0B, Student Voice Timeline - staff planner - EDITABLE

0C, Student Voice, the Staff Guide

01, Student Voice Timeline for students EDITABLE

02, Student Rep Briefing template EDITABLE

03, Student Voice, the Student Guide

04, SVM Survey - Guide to setting up - for staff

05, SVM feedback request slide EDITABLE

06, COMMENTS - RESPONSES DOC template EDITABLE

07, SVM 1 agenda template EDITABLE

08, ROLLING ACTION PLAN template EDITABLE

09, WHAT HAVE WE DONE WITH YOUR FEEDBACK slide template EDITABLE

10, SVM 2 agenda template EDITABLE

11, SVM 3 agenda template EDITABLE

12, Ongoing actions carried forward template EDITABLE
